

STUDIES ON THE NATURE OF RACEMIC MODIFICATIONS OF OPTI-
CALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN THE SOLID STATE. PART XVIII.
CAMPHANOQUINOXALINE, CAMPHANODIHYDROQUINOXA-
LINE, *m*- AND *p*-PHENYLENE-*bis*-IMINO- AND
-AMINOCAMPHORS

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The racemic forms of camphanoquinoxaline, *m*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors occurs racemates (*dl*), whereas those of camphanodihydroquinoxaline and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-imino-camphor exist as solid solutions. The stability of these racemic forms has been discussed with the aid of their melting point—composition diagrams.

In this communication we have discussed the nature of racemic modifications of camphanoquinoxaline, camphanodihydroquinoxaline, *m*- and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors.

By the application of Roozeboom's phase rule method of the melting point-composition diagrams to the mixtures of racemic and *dextro* forms of these substances, the racemic forms have been diagnosed as true *dl* compounds or *solid solutions* according as these diagrams consist of three curves or a single curve. No example of the racemic form occurring as *mixture*, providing two curves in the melting point—composition diagrams, has been found in the present study.

Excepting the *p*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -amino-*dl*-camphors, all the other racemic forms described herein are new substances.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Camphanoquinoxalines were prepared both by the method of Singh and Mazumder (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 566) and also by heating the equimolecular mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine and camphorquinone in dry state with an excess of anhydrous sodium sulphate on a water-bath for an hour, the latter method affording the better yield.

For the preparation of camphanodihydroquinoxaline from the corresponding camphanoquinoxaline, reduction of the ethereal solution of the latter with zinc dust and 10% KOH was found to be more satisfactory than the Sn-HCl method used by Singh *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1920, 117, 980). The melting points of *d*-camphanoquinoxaline and its reduction product, *d*-camphanodihydroquinoxaline, are found to agree with those reported earlier (*loc. cit.*), but the rotatory power of *d*-camphanodihydroquinoxaline is found to be much higher, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ in chloroform, -212.5 (reported -175°).

m-Phenylene-bis-iminocamphor (Singh and Mazumder, *loc. cit.*), *p*-phenylene-bis-imino- and -aminocamphors (Singh and Bhaduri, this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 545) were prepared according to methods described. The melting points of the *dextro* isomers of *m*-phenylene-bis imino- and -aminocamphors (Table I) differ considerably from those reported earlier (150.51° and 163° respectively). The rotatory powers of these compounds are, however, in good agreement with the reported values.

Known proportions of *dextro* and racemic forms were powdered intimately in an agate mortar and the melting point of each composition was determined as the mean of six readings taken with a Siebert and Kühn thermometer, graduated in 0.1° . The experimental results are represented in the form of curves (Figs. 1 and 2) in which the melting points are plotted against composition.

DISCUSSION

Camphanoquinoxaline (Fig. 1, a).—This diagram consists of three curves DE₁, E₁RE₂ and E₂L, which shows that the racemic form is a true *dl* compound. The range of existence of the racemic form is great which is indicated by the central portion of the diagram occupying a large area, almost the whole of the diagram.

FIG. 1

m-Phenylene-bis-*iminocamphor* (Fig. 1, b).—In this case also the diagram consists of three curves and the racemic form is shown to be a true *dl* compound. It has a fair range of existence. No appreciable dissociation of the racemic form into its optically active components is shown as the central portion of the diagram is steep. The horizontal portion of the curve *dl-d* between the composition ranges 30 *dl* : 70 *d* to 50 *dl* : 50 *d* shows that the racemic form affords a solid solution with the active form in this region.

p-Phenylene-bis-*iminocamphor* (Fig. 1, c) and *Camphanodihydroquinoxaline* (Fig. 2, a).—Each of these diagrams consists of a single continuous curve without any *singular* point on it and is concave to the composition axis. The racemic forms of each of these compounds are therefore *solid solutions* of equimolecular quantities of the *dextro* and *laevo* forms.

FIG. 2

m-Phenylene-bis-*aminocamphor* (Fig. 2, b).—This also shows the typical characteristics of the racemic form, being a true *dl* compound. The eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 , are sharp and well defined. The central portion is somewhat rounded which shows that the racemic form partially dissociates into its component active forms at its melting point.

TABLE I
Physical properties and chemical analyses of compounds.

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	Colour and cryst. form.	% Nitrogen. Found.	% Nitrogen. Calc.	Remarks.
1.	Camphanoxinoxalines $C_{16}H_{14}N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 74.0^\circ \\ dl. \quad 80.5^\circ \end{array} \right.$	Colorless thin rectangular plates " prismatic needles	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 12.02 \\ 11.98 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 11.76 \\ \end{array} \right.$	Highly soluble in all the organic solvents. Insoluble in water.
2.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -iminocamphors $C_{26}H_{34}O_2N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 166.5^\circ \\ dl. \quad 171.0^\circ \end{array} \right.$	Yellow prismatic needles Do	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 7.15 \\ 7.22 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 6.93 \\ \end{array} \right.$	Highly soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone; less so in methyl alcohol. ethyl alcohol and ethyl acetate; insoluble in water.
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -iminocamphors $C_{26}H_{34}O_2N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 268.5^\circ \\ dl. \quad 259.5^\circ \end{array} \right.$	Golden yellow spindles " " thin rectangular plates	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 7.16 \\ 7.18 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 6.93 \\ \end{array} \right.$	
4.	Camphanodihydroquinoxaline $C_{16}H_{20}N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 213.0^\circ \\ dl. \quad 193.0^\circ \end{array} \right.$	Colorless long silky needles " " fine " "	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 11.91 \\ 11.94 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 11.67 \\ \end{array} \right.$	Highly soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, ethyl acetate, less so in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol; insoluble in water.
5.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -aminocamphors $C_{26}H_{34}O_2N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 175.0^\circ \\ dl. \quad 173.0^\circ \end{array} \right.$	" prismatic " " silky leaflets	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 7.13 \\ 7.12 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 6.86 \\ \end{array} \right.$	
6.	<i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -aminocamphors $C_{26}H_{34}O_2N_2$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d. \quad 208.0^\circ \\ dl. \quad 210.2^\circ \end{array} \right.$	" prismatic needles " Do	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 7.14 \\ 7.14 \end{array} \right.$	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 6.86 \\ \end{array} \right.$	

p-Phenylene-bis-aminocamphor.—The different mixtures of the *dextro* and racemic modifications of this substance do not have any definite and sharp melting points. It is therefore not possible to draw any conclusion about the nature of its racemic form.

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